

**INSTILLING CHARACTER VALUES IN EARLY CHILDHOOD
IN THE PERSPECTIVE OF CURRICULUM AND PARENTING
(MULTI-SITE STUDY IN PAUD ISLAM SABILAL MUHTADIN
AND PAUD MAWADDAH, BANJARMASIN, INDONESIA)**

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Abstract:

Instilling character values since early childhood is a responsibility of parents, educators, tutors, society, and government. For this reason, togetherness, harmony, and partnership in instilling the character values from early childhood must be supported and optimized together. Therefore, this article will discuss the implementation of character values in early childhood in the perspective of the curriculum and parenting of parents at PAUD Islam Sabilal Muhtadin and PAUD Mawaddah, Banjarmasin. Both of these schools apply the implementation of character values through curriculum and parenting parents. This study used the qualitative technique with exposure of informant finding in descriptive. Data collection techniques in this research is by observing participant, interview deeply and documentation analysis. This research was conducted more than one site with the different characteristic (multisite). Based on the results of the analysis of the study, it is concluded that: 1) Implementation of curriculum management supports the implementation of character values in PAUD Islam Sabilal Muhtadin and PAUD Islam Mawaddah Banjarmasin integrated into learning activities in groups and the center of the curriculum are made before the early semester, it is made by the headmaster as well as teacher, and it is made according to the stages of students development 2) Implementation of the program management is carried between school and parents in implementing of parenting through parenting's activity, family day and other activities 3) Implementation strategies which are used in character education in both schools are habituation, exemplary, assignment, direction and conditioning (cultural).

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1. Introduction

The development of national character is one of the things that is very much considered by the government so that it should be welcomed and formulated systematic and comprehensive steps for its implementation in the education process. The character of the nation is very dependent on the quality of the character of its human resources (HR), therefore quality characters need to be established and fostered from an early age. According to Freud the failure to plant good personality at an early age will form a troubled person in his later adulthood (Masnur, 2013). Early Childhood Education is expected to be a strong foundation to shape the attitude and character of students. Its implementation in 2013 Early Childhood Education Curriculum.

Samani, (2013) states that "*Character is an attribute or characteristics that shape and differentiate personal characteristics / ethical characteristics, and mental complexity of a group or nation.*" Meanwhile, The Free Dictionary in its online site, defines character as a combination of qualities or characteristics that distinguish a person or group or an object from another. Character, is also defined as a "*description of a person's attributes, characteristics, or abilities. By knowing the existence of a character, one can estimate his reactions, to various phenomena that arise in him or his relationships with others, in various circumstances, and as controlling them.*" Based on the statements of the experts, the character is a personality picture that is owned by someone who is caused by the environment in their daily lives.

Early age education is the initial foundation in shaping the character of children. However, the implementation has not been able to run optimally. Early age education is still oriented towards developing academic abilities alone, not in developing the character and aspects of child development, so that this clearly violates the nature of early childhood education which should aim at developing all the potential and basic intelligence possessed by every child. Indonesia is currently facing a severe problem that must be overcome, namely the occurrence of a prolonged multidimensional crisis. According to Opinion (Suyadi, 2013), in Indonesia the implementation of character education today is felt to be urgent, this is due to the phenomenon of rampant news about such as narcotics, brawls, protests, pornography and various other irregularities that are not in accordance with the norms and ethics in the community.

The above problems are some of the problems found and the increase towards the negative is also smaller than the increase in positive values, but the fact is, it provides enough information about the low character of students and increases concerns about the development of the character, character and morality of students. The quality of the learning process becomes the object of the first accusation against the low character of students. Learning designer experts place a step in analyzing student

characteristics in a very important position before the selection and development step of learning, especially in terms of the learning curriculum.

The problem of character values that occur in early childhood based on the observations of the authors in the field is the lack of children's ability in aspects of responsibility, communicative and cooperation. This can be seen in children's behavior when it is difficult to express their desires or opinions and speak loudly and high-pitched to their friends, both when doing learning and when playing. In addition, children are still not able to carry out activities together, dominate an activity in learning, are still seen fighting over toys, and have not been able to take turns. This situation often occurs almost every day, and one of the causes is television content that presents a lot of scenes that smell like violence.

Instilling character values from an early age is a shared responsibility between parents, educators, caregivers, communities, and the government. For this reason, togetherness, harmony, and partnerships especially between schools and parents in instilling character values from an early age must be gathered and optimized together. Cooperation with parents can be done through socialization so that the character values that have been familiarized in PAUD institutions can also be done at home. Educators / caregivers can apply the curriculum that contains the character building of early childhood. For the community and government, it is hoped that support can also be obtained by forming an atmosphere that is conducive to the formation of character for early childhood.

Seeing the role of character education in early childhood education, researchers selected two PAUD institutions that were equally involved in learning activities in character education, namely PAUD Islam Sabilal Muhtadin Banjarmasin and PAUD Islam Mawaddah Banjarmasin. Thus the focus and formulation of this research is how the implementation of curriculum management in supporting the planting of character values in Sabilal Muhtadin and PAAW Mawaddah in Banjarmasin City PAUD, How is the implementation of program management carried out jointly between schools and parents in the implementation of proper parenting to support the planting of character values in Sabilal Muhtadin and PAAW Mawaddah Banjarmasin City PAUD Islam and How the implementation strategy of planting character values in PAUD Islam Sabilal Muhtadin and PAUD Mawaddah City of Banjarmasin.

2. Methods

The research approach used is qualitative research with multi-site research design. The purpose of this study is to identify and describe the implementation of curriculum management in supporting the planting of character values, the implementation of program management carried out jointly between schools and parents in the implementation of appropriate parenting to support the cultivation of character values and the implementation strategy of values character values in PAUD Islam Sabilal

Muhtadin and PAUD Mawaddah Kota Banjarmasin in supporting the planting of character values.

This research was carried out in two PAUD institutions namely Sabilal Muhtadin Integrated Islamic PAUD in Banjarmasin. Data collection techniques are carried out through observation, interviews and documentation studies (Sugiyono, 2006). In qualitative research, the presence of researchers in the field is very important because researchers act as key instruments as well as research data collectors (Moleong, 2005).

To establish the validity of the data, researchers used criteria: credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability (Akbar & Usman, 2009). In this case, data analysis techniques used by researchers are data analysis techniques according to Miles and Huberman, consisting of: (1) data reduction, (2) data presentation, (3) drawing conclusions/verification.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 General description of Integrated Islamic PAUD Sabilal Muhtadin and Mawaddah Islamic PAUD

First, Integrated Islamic PAUD Sabilal Muhtadin Banjarmasin is under the auspices of the National Education Agency and is organized by the Sabilal Muhtadin Islamic Institute Foundation Banjarmasin. Integrated Islamic PAUD Sabilal Muhtadin Banjarmasin organizes formal education, namely Toddler (age 2-3 years), Play Group (ages 3-4 years), Kindergarten A (ages 4-5 years) and Kindergarten B (ages 5-6 years) and has a vision that is, "*The realization of a high-quality, high-competitiveness and rooted society in Islamic integration*". While the mission is "*Through children's play activities can develop all aspects of their development such as Affection, Cognition, Language, Physical and social children, to be ready to follow the next level of education*". In addition to the vision and mission, Sabilal Muhtadin Integrated Islamic PAUD has goals, including: 1) Faith and Devotion, 2) Good character, 3) Physical and Spiritual Health, 4) Knowledgeable and skilled, 5) Personality and independence and 6) Responsible for the development of the people and nation.

To achieve this vision, mission and purpose, Sabilal PAUD is supported by educational staff who have 2 Master's (S2) Academic qualifications, 2 Teachers (S1) and 2 Teachers (S1), who are currently completing a Bachelor of PAUD Education program at Lambung Mangkurat University, Banjarmasin.

Second, PAUD Islam Mawaddah Banjarmasin is run by the Ministry of Education and organized by the Sakinah Foundation. PAUD Islam Mawaddah Banjarmasin organizes formal education, namely the Play Group (ages 2-4 years), Kindergarten A (ages 4-5 years) and Kindergarten B (ages 5-6 years) and has a vision that is, "Growing, Rooted, Fruitful" is the motto that underlies the vision of the Mawaddah Banjarmasin PAUD, which can be explained as follows: "*making the entire PAUD Mawaddah Banjarmasin community (students, educators, managers, parents of students, and foundations) to grow according to their respective roles. physically and mentally,*

and produce benefits for the surrounding community, especially in the field of Islamic religious education". Whereas the mission, among others:

1. Participate in the Indonesian government program in educating the life of the nation.
2. Develop the child's full potential with all the multiple intelligences he has brought from birth.
3. Develop and implement innovative and creative learning programs with the fields of development: Moral / Islamic Religion, Cognitive, Language, Physical Motoric, Independence, and Socialization Ability (Akhlaqul Karimah).
4. Develop and implement a child-centered learning program, in accordance with the uniqueness of individual children and the stage of development.
5. Develop and implement learning programs that make students enjoy learning.
6. Develop learning programs that make the entire PAUD Mawaddah Banjarmasin community (students, educators, managers, and parents of students) as Lifelong Learners.
7. Education for all groups, by making PAUD Mawaddah Banjarmasin an educational institution that is open to all children with diverse Islamic and economic backgrounds, as well as children with special needs.

To achieve the vision, mission and goals, PAUD Sabilal is supported by educational staff who have 10 academic qualifications for undergraduate (S1) graduates and 3 Teachers of DII. In this case, according to the Minister of National Education Regulation No. 58 of 2009 concerning the Standards of Early Childhood Education, it is stated that early childhood educators are professionals who are tasked with planning, implementing the learning process and assessing learning outcomes and conducting guidance, nurturing and protection of students.

3.2 Implementation of curriculum management in supporting the planting of character values in PAUD Islam Sabilal Muhtadin and PAUD Mawaddah Banjarmasin City

Based on the results of observations that were strengthened by interviews and documentation studies, it was found that the character values implemented in both schools were character values derived from the Qur'an, Sunnah and Pancasila. Planting character values is the basis for the formation of annual vision, mission, goals, curriculum, learning programs and programs. The purpose of education for both schools is to form a person who is faithful and devoted to Allah SWT and has a noble character in accordance with the teachings of Islam. The curriculum used is the curriculum of each school's characteristics, namely the Islamic character values where the 2013 curriculum is used as a role model or reference. In addition to formulating the school's vision, mission and goals. The school curriculum and program are also planned and arranged with the aim of achieving the goals and objectives of Education, namely Planting character values. This is in accordance with that expressed by Zakiah Darajat in his book Islamic Education, that the curriculum is seen as "*an Education program that is*

planned and implemented to achieve a number of educational goals" (Salahudin & Alkrienciehie, 2013).

According to Suriansyah (2011) the success in achieving the goals of character education is not only determined by the foundations in learning but also by the elements in it, namely students, educators, the interaction of students and educators, the environment, material/educational content. Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System states that the curriculum is a set of plans and arrangements regarding the objectives, contents, and learning materials as well as the methods used as guidelines for the implementation of learning activities to achieve certain educational goals. According to Mulyasa (2013) implementation of the 2013 Curriculum is expected to produce productive, creative and innovative people. This is possible, because this curriculum is based on character and competence, which conceptually has several advantages. First, 2013 curriculum uses a scientific approach, because departing, focuses and empties on the nature of students to develop various competencies according to their respective potential. In this case the student is the subject of learning, and the learning process takes place naturally in the form of work takes place naturally in the form of work and experience based on certain competencies, not transfer of knowledge (transfer of knowledge). Second, 2013 curriculum based on character and competence may underlie the development of other abilities. Mastery of science, and certain skills in a job, the ability to solve problems in everyday life, and the development of personality aspects can be done optimally based on certain competency standards. Third, there are certain fields of study or subjects which in their development are more appropriate to use the competency approach, especially those related to skills.

The curriculum in Indonesia is experiencing development starting in the 2013/2014 school year, namely the 2013 Curriculum. Referring to the findings in the field, curriculum planning/learning programs in PAUD Islam Sabilal Muhtadin and PAUD Islam Mawaddah Banjarmasin are both made at the end of the second semester after the report cards. Foundations, principals, teachers and employees all participate and participate in the planning process and the preparation of curriculum and learning programs. The learning program formulated includes the semester, weekly (RPM) and daily (RPPH)/lesson plan programs. besides also formulating an assessment plan and schedule of teaching and learning activities, learning methods / strategies and characters that will be taught to children. In making learning programs also adjusted to the stages of development of students.

This is certainly an added value possessed by Islamic PAUD Sabilal Muhtadin and PAUD Mawaddah Banjarmasin. As revealed by Nazir (2013) the process of preparing learning material, the use of learning media, the use of learning approaches and methods, and the assessment of learning planning in one time allocation that will be carried out at certain times to achieve the learning objectives. Planning learning is something that is prepared systematically in a learning that will be shared with students that from the semester program is written in the RPPM and RPPH/lesson plan

that has been made by the teacher, which shows the calculation of time allocation related to effective days for one semester that is well programmed. Besides that, the schedule for teaching center teachers is also arranged so that the learning process also works better. From the findings in PAUD Islam Sabilal Muhtadin and PAUD Islam Mawaddah Banjarmasin, it can be seen that the two educational institutions have been planning and preparing the curriculum and learning programs well. Because the curriculum is a system of learning programs that are intended to achieve institutional goals in educational institutions, so the curriculum plays an important role in realizing a quality or quality school.

This is in accordance with what was expressed by Rusman (2014) Learning Implementation Plans are outlined in the syllabus to direct student learning activities in an effort to achieve basic competencies. This is also in line with opinion opinions (Sofyan, 2013), namely: Every teacher who carries out learning activities is required to compile a complete and systematic RPP so that learning takes place in an interactive, inspiring, fun, challenging, motivating students to actively participate, and provide space sufficient for initiative, creativity and independence according to the talents, interests and physical and psychological development of students. The RPP is prepared for each KD used in one meeting or more. Thus, what is in the RPP must contain matters that are directly related to learning activities in an effort to achieve mastery of a basic competency. From the results of interviews, observations and documentation it can be seen that there are character values in the learning curriculum and program at PAUD Islam Sabilal Muhtadin and PAUD Islam Mawaddah Banjarmasin. this is in accordance with the values used by the two PAUDs, namely the Qur'an, Sunnah and Pancasila. So that the curriculum is expected to be able to achieve the school's goal of forming faithful students who are devoted to Allah SWT, having good morals, physically and mentally healthy, intelligent, knowledgeable and skilled, personable and independent in their daily attitudes and behavior.

The preparation of curriculum and learning programs is carried out at the end of the semester or before the start of the new semester. And in the preparation it involves all the teaching staff in Sabilal Muhtadin PAUD Islam and Mawaddah PAUD Islam, because the preparation of curriculum and learning programs is adapted to the development of students according to their group and age. For the implementation of the planting of integrated character values in children's learning activities at school, both activities in groups and centers.

3.2 Implementation of Program management carried out jointly between schools and parents in the implementation of appropriate parenting in PAUD Islam Sabilal Muhtadin and PAUD Mawaddah Banjarmasin City

National education functions to develop the ability and shape of dignified national character and civilization in order to educate the life of the nation, aims to develop the potential of students to become believers and fear of God, noble, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become a democratic and responsible citizen.

Therefore, the participation of all parties is needed to realize the functions and objectives of the national education. One of the parties responsible for implementing the functions and objectives of national education is the family.

The family as the environment that is closest to students is the first place of education for him. The family has a very important role in the formation of the character of discipline in students. This is because a harmonious relationship between families will help smooth the process of education of a person, especially family members. As revealed in a survey conducted by the Ministry of National Education's Ministry of National Education (Wibowo, 2013), states that: On average students attending school are only about 7 hours per day, or less than 30 percent. The rest or around 70 percent, students are in the family and the surrounding environment. When viewed from the aspect of time quantity, education in schools only contributes only 30 percent to the results of student education. In addition to school, the role of the family is no less important in the formation of a student's character.

School as a place to formally study a student is expected to be able to provide mental development. The role of teachers is not just as a teacher, academic educators but also educators of character, morals, and culture for their students (Daryanto and Suryatri 2013: 11). Lickona (in Daryanto and Suryatri 2013: 11), schools and teachers must educate characters. Referring to the findings in the field regarding the program carried out jointly between schools and parents in the implementation of proper parenting in supporting the planting of character values, one form of parental support for this character planting program is by performing a ritual prayer with parents at home every Friday night.

The results of these activities are collected by their respective classroom teachers as proof that parents and children have done their work. The results of the activity can be in the form of photos collected through whatsapp groups and written reports the next day. From the interview results also obtained information that it turns out that not only school residents are obliged to plant character values in children, parents must also be involved in planning the character values in early childhood because parents are the ones who have plenty of time with children. Parents of students are very supportive in the process of planting character values. Among them with enthusiasm, parents take part in activities carried out by the community such as family day activities, rituals of Hajj, and other activities. At the beginning of the semester parenting activities are always carried out, the purpose of which is to provide socialization to students' parents about planting characters for early childhood and there is a consultation day for parents every three months. With support from parents, planting character values that are expected to be achieved.

According to Suriansyah (2011) In planning school development parents can also participate. Parents can participate in providing funds, infrastructure and school facilities as an effort to realize school programs that have been jointly prepared (Suriansyah, 2015). Parental involvement in joint events is an activity that involves parents in carrying out outing activities. The purpose of this activity is: To bring the

relationship between parents, children and educational institutions closer and increase the role of parents in the learning process. If this can run well and continuous eating is expected to strengthen the planting of character in children.

3.3 Strategy implementation of character values in PAUD Islam Sabilal Muhtadin and PAUD Mawaddah City of Banjarmasin

Based on the findings, it is known that students and educators become an important element in the success of planting character values. As educators must be able to interact and communicate well with students. Because the success of good interaction in the learning process will determine the success of students in mastering the material provided. Therefore, educators must have good communication skills with students, using tools to facilitate the communication process and have the ability to arouse passion in the process of interaction with students so that it becomes a conducive atmosphere for the implementation of the learning process (Suriansyah, 2011).

This condition requires school managers to improve the quality of learning through improving the quality of teaching staff through workshop programs, internship programs and so on. Indra Jati (2001) revealed that teachers are not only teachers, but also as coaches, counselors, and learning managers. As a trainer the teacher encourages students to work hard and achieve the highest achievement, helping to appreciate the value of learning and knowledge. As a counselor the teacher acts as a student friend to become a role model in a person who contains respect and intimacy from students. As a learning manager, the teacher guides students to always learn, take initiatives and issue their ideas. (Suriansyah, 2011).

Briefing as well as example/example. Because according to Vernon A. Magnesen, 90% of the learning process is through what we say and do (Salahudin & Alkrienciehie, 2013). Based on this, it can be seen that students are easier to understand the material given through verbal instruction, then given examples that can be seen directly, and the child also practices it. Through this way the character planting will be more attached and embedded in the memories and thoughts of children. As expressed by Joseph Joubert "*Children need models more than they need critics.*" This means that children need more examples than reprimand or criticism (Widayanti, 2012).

In the school environment, all school residents must give the students room to form activities that support character building, such as bulletins or guidebooks for parents and parenting activities (Najib, Wiyani, & Sholichin, 2016). Like the Chicago Child-Parent Center has to offer, parenting does not only focus on children, but also on parents, and it shows long-term results that are very positive for parents and children (Reynolds & Kamphaus, 2004). The results of a study by Golan, Spiker & Sumi (2005) also show that parents who attend parenting education classes have better care and their children show better cognitive and social skills in school and readiness (Murray, McFarland-Piazza, & Harrison, 2015).

In addition, the school environment must reflect the formation of students 'character by carrying out various activities and supplementing everything related to

the formation of students' character formation, such as syiar, facilities and infrastructure (Salahudin & Alkrienciehie, 2013).

So the pattern of character education that can be done at school is:

1. Give a good example
2. Provide motivation to children
3. Work together to shape characters both at school and at home
4. Raising internal motivation from child learners
5. Schools must be a model of society that is peaceful and harmonious
6. Schools must provide opportunities for students to practice moral behavior (Salahudin & Alkrienciehie, 2013).

The implementation or application of planting character values is carried out after the planning and preparation of the curriculum. it can be said that this implementation process is a process of realizing what has been planned, namely the character value curriculum and learning learning program.

From the findings in the research location, it can be obtained information that PAUD Islam Sabilal Muhtadin and PAUD Mawaddah have an implementation strategy for planting similar character values, including:

a. Habituation

The applied habituation method is quite effective in training students to do good things. All activities in school from the time the child enters the school environment to go home from school are always accustomed to following the rules or operational standards that have been determined. where the rules are arranged based on character values derived from religious values (Al-Qur'an and Sunnah) and the value of Pancasila.

b. Exemplary

Exemplary is exemplified by all Teachers, employees and anyone who enters the School. This method is very effective in applying the character-based cultivation of religious values because the best education is by doing, not just talking about. Moreover, early childhood are excellent imitators, so if given a good example the children will follow the good example.

c. Briefing

Every job is always preceded by a briefing from the teacher. It is also applied in education, allowing students to understand its philosophical values from what is done. For example when eating activities, before eating the teacher always gives directions to line up hand washing, sit in an orderly manner, pray before and after meals, eat with your right hand and do not speak while eating and clean the cutlery after eating. Then explained also the reason why we have to wash our hands before eating, why should we pray before and after meals, why not eat while talking and so on. this is done so that the children understand the intent and purpose of not just carrying out the task without knowing its meaning.

d. Assignment

Assignment is also an effective way of implementing the planting of character values. Assignment is not only done to students, but also to students' parents. As was done by PAUD Islam Mawaddah who gave assignments to Parents to provide time on Thursday night to worship with children (evening prayer, Islamic prayer and recitation). In addition, during parenting, both PAUD Islam Sabilal or PAUD Islam Mawaddah are both always socializing the importance of the role of parents in participating in providing home education, especially character education. The aim is that the planting of character in children is always consistent and continuous so that the cultivation of character values in children is stronger and stickier until they are adults.

e. Environmental Creation (Culture)

A conducive school environment is also effective in supporting the process of applying character values. All school residents provide examples that reflect the value of Islamic character. In the school environment there are also many posters that reflect the value of Islamic characters. All activities carried out also reflect the character of Islamic values. Thus these conditions create learning conditions that are healthy, enjoyable and of Islamic character. everything that is heard, seen and felt by students is an element that educates and shapes their character according to the teachings of Islam. Of all the strategies carried out in the application of religious value-based character education in the two educational institutions in accordance with what is mentioned by Najib, et al (2016) the implementation of character education through habituation activities is done by:

1. Routine habits;
2. Spontaneous habituation;
3. Exemplary habits;
4. Conditioning.

Indicators of achieving success in planting character values are not only judged by students but also from school culture. This is in accordance with the statement of Jamal Ma'mur Asmani, namely the criteria for achieving the successful implementation of character education in schools is the formation of school culture, namely behavior, daily habits, and symbols that are practiced by school residents and communities around the school based on character values (Asmani, 2013).

4. Conclusion

The conclusions obtained from the research conducted are: 1) Implementation of curriculum management in supporting the planting of character values in Sabilal Muhtadin Islamic PAUD and Mawaddah Banjarmasin Islamic PAUD integrated in learning activities both in groups and in curriculum centers made before the new school year, made together by principals and teachers and made according to children's development stages 2) Implementation of program management carried out jointly between schools and parents in the implementation of appropriate parenting is carried out through parenting, family day activities and other activities 3) Implementation

strategies used in education the characters in both schools are habituation, exemplary, assignment, direction and environmental conditioning (culture).

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